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DEFINITION OF PLAYER’S STATUS AND ITS IMPACT ON THE ECONOMIC VALUE OF FOOTBALL PLAYER EMPLOYMENT CONTRACTS

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ANNOTATION

From an economic perspective football player employment contracts have always been significant, as players can make profits for their clubs and themselves by plying their trade in the football industry. Recently some of the scholars have been working on this topic. The definition of a player and its importance in establishing him as professional or amateur will determine whether football players gets remunerated for his service as a professional. This paper covers some of the most important research works on the given issue, mainly examining the definition of a football player’s status and its potential impact on the employment contracts of football players.

Key words: FIFA RSTP, FIFA DRC, FIFA PSC, CAS, scholarship agreement, Sporting training agreement, professional athlete, professional sport.

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FUTBOLCHINING MAQOMI TUSHUNCHASI VA UNING FUTBOLCHILAR MEHNAT SHARTNOMALARINING IQTISODIY QIYMATIGA TA'SIRI

ANNOTATSIYA

Iqtisodiy nuqtai nazardan, futbolchilarning mehnat shartnomalari har doim hal juda muhim ahamiyatga ega bo‘lib keladi, chunki futbolchilar futbol sporti sohasida o‘z kasbi bilan shug‘ullanish orqali klublari va o‘zlari uchun daromad keltirishlari mumkin. So‘nggi paytlarda ba‘zi olimlar ushbu mavzu ustida ishlar olib bormoqda. Futbolchining ta‘rifi va uni professional yoki havaskor sifatida belgilashdagi ahamiyati futbolchining professional xizmatlari uchun xaq oladimi yoki yo‘qligini aniqlab beradi. Ushbu maqola yuqoridagi masala bo‘yicha eng muhim tadqiqot ishlarini ko‘rib

chiqadi, asosan futbolchining maqomini aniqlash va uning futbolchilarning mehnat shartnomalariga potentsial ta'sirini ko'rib chiqadi.

Kalit soʻzlar: FIFA RSTP, FIFA DRC, FIFA PSC, CAS, stipendiya kelshuvi, sport mashg'ulotlari kelishuvi, professional sportchi, professional sport.

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ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ СТАТУСА ИГРОКА И ЕГО ВЛИЯНИЕ НА ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКУЮ ЦЕННОСТЬ ТРУДОВЫХ КОНТРАКТОВ ФУТБОЛИСТА

АННОТАЦИЯ

С экономической точки зрения трудовые контракты футболистов всегда имели большое значение, поскольку игроки могут получать прибыль для своих клубов и самих себя, занимаясь своей профессией в футбольной индустрии. В последнее время некоторые ученые работают над этой темой. Определение игрока и его важность для определения его как профессионала или любителя будут определять, получает ли футболист вознаграждение за свои профессиональные услуги. В этой статье рассматриваются некоторые из наиболее важных исследовательских работ по данному вопросу, в основном рассматривающие определение статуса футболиста и его потенциальное влияние на трудовые договоры футболистов.

Ключевые слова: FIFA RSTP, FIFA DRC, FIFA PSC, CAS, соглашение о стипендии, соглашение о спортивной подготовке, профессиональный спортсмен, профессиональный спорт.

Based on their social status and income they make football players can be differentiated as “football stars”, “average players”, but sometimes they may also be qualified as “amateur” and “professional” players depending on their talent and ability. It is essential for a player to acquire and maintain professional status in order to be eligible for compensation for training expenses. FIFA RSTP provides for definitions on what exactly means being amateur and professional players. Football players are regarded either amateurs or professionals. It is clearly expressed in Art.2 of the FIFA RSTP, “a professional is a player who has a written contract with a club and is paid more for his footballing activity than the expenses he effectively incurs”. [1] If either of the above mentioned requirements are not met, a player cannot be considered a professional, and the rest of the players are considered to be amateurs.

The fact that a player is registered within the association is not necessary in determining the status of a player, as the employment relations between a player and a club will only be based on the contractual relationships not the registration at the association concerned. As stated in Art.5 para 1 FIFA RSTP, in order to participate in any organized football, a player has to be registered electronically and possess FIFA ID.[2] However, the concept of maintaining contractual stability constitutes that only duly signed employment contracts will impose legally binding obligations on the parties.

National associations' regulations can also be referred to in terms of the player's "professional" status, however national associations' regulations contain remarkably similar provisions to those found in the FIFA RSTP. However, that does not mean that this superiority applies only to international transfers, it also to national transfers. Pursuant to Art. 1 para. 3, litt. a) and 26 para. 3 RSTP, it is compulsory for all the national federations literally transpose Art. 2 RSTP, which includes the worldwide mandatory definition of “professionals” and “amateurs.”[3] National legislation of Uzbekistan does not provide for clear definitions on “professional athlete”, there are some terms given to the “professional sport” but not professional athlete. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On

physical education and sports” explicitly establishes the definition of “professional sport” as “professional sports is part of the organization and conduct of sports competitions, in which athletes receive a reward and (or) salary for participating and preparing for them as their main activity”. [4] Another example, the definition of “professional sports” has been included in the Article 60 of the Ecuadorian Law of August 4, 2010, “On sports, physical education and recreation”, and it reads “professional sport includes activities that are rewarded and that are legally developed by sports organizations that search for and select talented athletes of high achievements”. [5] A similar norm contains the Article 55 of the Law of the Republic of Belarus on Physical Culture and Sports. And according to the previously mentioned law “professional sport” is defined as “professional sport is a part of sport that includes entrepreneurial, labor and other activities not prohibited by law, aimed at achieving high sports results and related to receiving rewards (income) from organizing sports events and (or) participating in them”. [6]

When the distinctions and definitions between professional and amateur athletes are compared, it becomes noticeable that few other countries' laws provide a precise understanding of what a professional sport is.

Most foreign countries' laws, on the other hand, have specific provisions that are related to amateur sports, which are found in the majority of cases. For instance, Article 19 of the Latvian Law (ed. of 09.07.2021) “On sports” of 24.10.2002, contains the definition of a professional athlete, according to which “a professional athlete is an individual who, on the basis of an employment contract and for an agreed remuneration, prepares for and participates in sports events.” [7] On the other hand, part 3 of Article 7 of the Law of the Autonomous Community of Madrid (Spain) of 12/28/1994 No. 15/1994 “On sports in the Autonomous Community of Madrid”, stipulates “professional athletes are those who directly or indirectly receive basic wages for participating in sports.” [8] As defined in section 4 of Article 1 of the Hungarian Law of 2004 "On Sports, “a professional athlete is one who competes in sports activities professionally for the purpose of earning income. All other athletes are amateurs.” One feature that distinguishes the Hungarian Law “On Sports” from those of other nations is that it contains a definition of amateur athletes, albeit in a restrictive sense. According to subparagraph 13 of paragraph 1 of the Additional Provisions of the Bulgarian Law “On Physical Education and Sports”, "Amateur athletes" are persons who carry out systematic training and competition activities, and for them this is not their main professional and/or do not receive remuneration for this activities.” [9] An amateur athlete is defined in Article 1 of Moroccan Law No. 30-09 "On Physical Culture and Sports" as "any athlete who does sports on a non-professional basis." [10] However, the Law of the Republic of Moldova of 25.03.1999 No. 330-XIV (ed. of 2016) "On Physical culture and sports" states "amateur athletes do not receive income from sports. Sports scholarships and allowances, daily allowances paid to trips, allocations for food, medicines and stimulants, as well as sports bonuses are not considered income”. [11]

By introducing the sentence “on a non-professional basis”, lawmakers must have meant athletes who do not perform for a fixed salary or profit, but rather for leisure reasons.

Some sports law scholars have also contributed to the advancement of the legal status of football players, particularly in the broader context of athletes. A. Tukmanov offered expert insight in his dissertation, which was quite similar to the definitions given above, stating:

“A professional football player is an athlete of a professional football team, for whom sports are the main activity, and who receives, in accordance with an employment contract with a sports professional club, a salary for preparing for sports competitions and for participating in them”. [12] O. Shevchenko notes that with the definition of the concept of a professional athlete it should be understood as an individual who has entered into an employment relationship, for whom sports are the main activity, which is part of a professional sports organization for sports, appropriately registered, included in the official register of license holders and has received a license. [13] The only distinction between the two definitions described above is the remuneration that an athlete may receive for his training and participation in professional sports. While Lean O’Leary believes that the “professionalism or receiving payment for participating in sport was analogous to being engaged in a trade and indicative of a master-servant relationship. The early administrators of football and rugby

union came from the middle classes and played the sports for leisure.”[14] It depicts the early days of professional and amateur football and establishes the distinction between them, taking into account the social status of the then-professional players and the amateurs who merely played for fun. In addition, O’Leary claims that players used to be compensated for their involvement and professionalism in football, which is comparable to the rules that were originally mentioned in FIFA Regulations on the transfer and status of players.

It should be noted that various gaps exist in Uzbekistan's national law governing the status of professional sports athletes, which must be addressed. As can be observed that the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On physical education and sports” and other legislative acts do not give a specific definition on the concept of professional athletes. Furthermore, the Labour Code of Uzbekistan does not contain any specific definitions regarding professional athletes, in particular football players.

One of the main criteria for assessing a player as a “professional” is whether the amount of money paid in wages is “more” than the expenses effectively incurred by the player. There is no concrete measure or amount defined in FIFA Regulations. In this regard, how the calculation of the amount should be done? Is it just much more? or just a little more? It is clear that the FIFA regulations do not stipulate a minimum wage. The player may still be considered a non-amateur (professional), even if he agrees to perform low-wage services. [15] Additionally, a player can be regarded a professional even though his salary is significantly less than the average salary in their country, or an amateur even if his salary surpasses the country's minimum wage.[15] The only aspect that matters is if the player's earnings surpass the player's effectively incurred expenses; the expenses to be evaluated and compared are not those related to the player's general cost of living, but those particularly and effectively incurred for his club football activities. While determining whether transfer compensation is due or not, it is crucial to differentiate between amateur and professional players, as training compensation is only payable when a player is deemed to be a professional.

FIFA DRC encourages that a player's status should be taken into account when evaluating an employment contract, regardless of any categorization used in the contract or by the member association involved. Considering that the Article 2 of the FIFA RSTP Regulations is mandatory at the national level, any conflicting national regulations are consequently irrelevant to a player's status. In a case Ref.nr.18-02527 of 06.02.2020, the FIFA DRC confirmed the "professional status" of a female player registered as an amateur in Italy. The Dispute Resolution Chamber determined that when assessing a player's status, the criteria set out in Article 2 paragraph 2 of the FIFA Regulations on the Status and Transfers of Players shall take precedence over any agreement between the parties containing contradictory provisions. In this dispute, the parties asserted that their agreement should be classified as an "agreement on reimbursement of costs for amateur sports activity," and that this fact does not establish their relationship as one of employment.[16] Even so, the FIFA deciding body concluded that the player meets the conditions set out in Article 2 para. 2 of the FIFA RSTP and that the female player must be considered as a "professional player." [16]

Oftentimes, a minimum wage agreed upon at the national football association level may exceed the amount expected to be incurred by a player throughout his early career stages. In a CAS case of 15 February 2017, CAS 2016/A/4603 SC Dinamo 1948 v. FC Internazionale Milano SpA, sole arbitrator established a Romanian player “at the age of 16 – was paid a minimum wage defined by the AIC (Italian Footballer’s Association) (i.e. EUR 14,086 a year), and it is established that the player received more for his footballing activity than the expenses he effectively incurred”.[17] Therefore, the sole arbitrator declared that the contract signed by the player and his club on 3 July 2013 was a professional contract.[17] It demonstrates that the player was earning more than he was spending, and thus meets the description of a professional player within the meaning of Article 2 of RSTP. However, it was noted that in some specific circumstances, monthly remuneration via so-called "scholarship agreements" resulted in some distinct approaches. For comparison purposes, the Court of Arbitration for Sport (CAS) has found that a player's monthly remuneration in the range of £400 British Pounds (GBP) exceeded the costs that were actually incurred by the player.[18] Based on that CAS ruling, it is reasonable to conclude that any player who engages in a scholarship agreement that provides for remuneration at or above that level will acquire professional status. In

contrast to that CAS award, a different approach has been adopted in a case involving Belgian and Portuguese football clubs (CAS 2014/A/3659 & 3660 & 3661 KSV Cercle Brugge v. Clube Linda-A-Velha & Club Uniao Desportiva e Recreativa de Alges & Sport Club Praiense).[19] Sole arbitrator ruled that the “the monthly flat-rate of EUR 400 reflects the average football-related costs of the Player in the season 2011 / 2012. Hence, the amount of EUR 400 does not constitute a salary or remuneration but only a refund for football-related costs”.[19] In that particular example, the player was only paid €400 per month for his expenses, with no further benefits such as allowances for accommodation, transport, and food at the club. Nevertheless Portugal has a different system of “Sports Training Agreements”, that indicates if a player receives EUR 250 per month in wages plus including food and accommodation then he is considered a professional player.

The status of players can be vital in maintaining contractual stability in employment relations between players and clubs. In transfer relations, only those clubs who registered players under professional status would be entitled to receive the transfer fees. Under the circumstances, if other big clubs tap one of the players of any club up and he secretly agrees the terms with a new club, then the former club can claim for compensation that its player breached his employment contract without just cause. However, in the case of amateurs this rule does not work even if the amateur player acquires a professional status in his new club.[20]

Conclusion

Relying on the research results, the authors assert that the economic aspects of football player employment contracts are of a great importance. Some of the factors that can be considered as integral part of the employment contracts of football players, that can make a great impact on the economic value of player employment contracts are such as status of players, transfer of players, training compensation, solidarity payments, and image rights.

FIFA Member associations' regulations can also be referred to in terms of the player's "professional" status, however national associations' regulations contain remarkably similar provisions to those found in the FIFA RSTP. However, that does not mean that this superiority applies only to international transfers, it also to national transfers. Pursuant to Art. 1 para. 3, litt. a) and 26 para. 3 RSTP, it is compulsory for all the national federations literally transpose Art. 2 RSTP, which includes the worldwide mandatory definition of “professionals” and “amateurs.”

Furthermore, it should be highlighted that Uzbekistan's national legislation regulating the status of professional athletes contains several loopholes that must be addressed. As can be seen, the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On physical education and sports" and other legislative acts do not provide a concrete definition of the concept of professional athletes, while there are terminology for "professional sport" but none for "professional athlete. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On physical education and sports” explicitly establishes the definition of “professional sport” as “professional sports is part of the organization and conduct of sports competitions, in which athletes receive a reward and (or) salary for participating and preparing for them as their main activity”.

According to research findings, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On physical education and sports" does not provide any definition of professional and amateur football players. Nevertheless, by referring to FIFA RSTP, definition of the professional football player could be established, but it still does not give complete meaning to what professional player is. According to RSTP one of the main criteria for assessing a player as a “professional” is whether the amount of money paid in wages is “more” than the expenses effectively incurred by the player. There is no concrete measure or amount defined in FIFA Regulations.

Article 15 of FIFA RSTP and UFA RSTP do not stipulate any complete definition of “established professional”, same time law of Uzbekistan “On physical culture and sports does not include a provision on “professional athlete” let alone “professional football player”. Taking into account, we suggest inserting into the laws of Uzbekistan and regulations of Uzbekistan Football Association certain norms, which establish full definition of “established professional” and “professional player” and “amateurs”.

Latest edition of the Labour Code and legislation of Uzbekistan cannot offer legal definition on professional football players and their employment. It would also play significant role to develop definitions if it was included as a separate chapter and articles which could be devoted for football players` status whether its amateurs or professionals.

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